

MULTIFUNCTIONAL STRUCTURAL POWER COMPOSITES BASED ON CARBON AEROGEL MODIFIED HIGH PERFORMANCE CARBON FIBRE FABRICS

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1 Introduction

Carbon fibre-reinforced polymer composite materials have made a huge impact, particularly in the aerospace and oil/gas industries since the 1960s, due to their light weight and excellent mechanical performance [1]. Recently, interest in multifunctional composite materials has increased rapidly [2]. Here, we report the development of new multifunctional composites by forming a supercapacitor from structural fibre composite laminates; each cell of the proposed structural supercapacitor consists of two modified structural carbon fibre fabric electrodes, separated by a structural glass fibre fabric, infused with a multifunctional polymeric electrolyte [3, 4]. Such composites allows the combination of energy storage systems into structural low weight components, which could significantly reduce the weight and volume of systems requiring electrical energy storage by simultaneously serving as load-carrying structural body. Our multifunctional composite design is useful for a wide range of applications, such as aerospace, electric/hybrid ground transport and portable electronics, where battery life and power management are limiting issues.

A crucial requirement for efficient structural power composites is the development of structural carbon fibre electrode materials that possess high energy storage and stable electrochemical performance whilst under mechanical load. Various strategies have been studied in our research group, including both chemical activation [5, 6] and carbon nanotube (CNT) grafting [7, 8]. Apparent improvements have been observed in specific surface area. However, these methods involve etching/damage of the carbon fibre surface by either the activating chemicals or

the catalyst for growing CNTs; process parameters need to be carefully controlled to avoid degradation of the fibre mechanical properties and the total volume available for the active material is limited. In the present work, a multifunctional electrode material is developed by embedding structural carbon fibre fabrics in a continuous network of carbon aerogel (CAG) to form a coherent but porous monolith [9]. CAGs are porous materials consisting of a three dimensional network of interconnected nanometre-sized particles with small interstitial pores, leading to typical surface areas of 400-1100 m²/g [10]. By combining structural carbon fibres with high surface area CAGs, the resulting hierarchical structure can provide good energy storage capacity, and also serve as mechanical reinforcement to the matrix in the multifunctional composites. A ‘proof-of-concept’ study of multifunctional structural power composites based on these CAG-modified carbon fabrics has been carried out: both electrochemical and mechanical properties of the composites is provided, together with a discussion of the prospects for this new form of multifunctional structural power composite.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

HTA 3k carbon fibre fabrics (plain weave, 200 g/m², TISSA Glasweberei AG) and glass fibre fabrics (plain weave, 200 g/m², TISSA Glasweberei AG) were used as the electrode and separator reinforcement materials, respectively. All chemical reagents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, and were used as-received.

2.2 Fabrication of CAG-modified carbon fabrics and structural power composites

Aerogels were fabricated based on the sol-gel polycondensation of resorcinol-formaldehyde (RF), with R:F ratio at 1:2. Potassium hydroxide (KOH) was used as the catalyst (C) and the R:C molar ratio was 50:1. The weight percentage of the RF in mixture was controlled to be 40% by adjusting the quantity of the diluent distilled water. The RF solution was prepared using the commercially-available RF resin (AX2000, INDSPEC Chemical Corporation) and then infused into the carbon fibre fabrics using resin infusion under flexible tooling (RIFT). The cured and dried specimens were then carbonised to CAGs at 800°C for 30 min in a furnace (Lenton ECF 12/30) under N₂.

2.3 Characterisation of CAG-modified carbon fabrics and structural power composites

The microstructure of the carbon fabrics before and after CAG modification was characterised using a field emission gun scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (Gemini LEO 1525 FEG-SEM), operating at 5 kV, without metal coating. Specific surface area of carbon fabrics were studied using a Micromeritics TriStar 3000 analyser with pure N₂. Cyclic voltammetry (CV) tests were performed using a SI 1287 electrochemical interface (Solartron Instruments); a three-electrode cell was used (platinum wire counter electrode, silver-silver chloride reference electrode and 3M KCl aqueous solution). The scan range (potential window) of -0.2 V to 0.2 V was used.

2.4 Fabrication of structural power composites

The layup for producing multifunctional structural power composites consisted of two carbon fabric electrodes, which sandwiched two glass fibre fabrics as the separator. To produce a multifunctional electrolyte matrix, 10 wt.% ionic liquid, 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl) imide (EMITFSI, purity ≥ 98%), was mixed into polyethylene glycol diglycidyl ether (PEGDGE, 82.6 wt.%), with a stirrer bar, until a homogeneous solution was obtained. Tri-ethylene-tetramine (TETA, 7.4 wt.%) was then added to the solution. The resin mixture was degassed and then infused into the vacuum bag containing the fabrics layup. The curing of specimens was performed at 80°C for 24 h.

2.5 Electrochemical characterisation of structural power composites

Electrochemical performance of structural power composites was studied via charge-discharge experiments that performed at room temperature using a SI 1287 electrochemical interface (Solartron Instruments) with a 0.1 V step voltage applied for 60 s. The dimensions of the composite devices were around 6.5×7.5 cm. Electrical characteristics were evaluated based on a simplified electrical equivalent circuit of the system (Fig. 1). The capacitance, C_{sp}, and resistances, R_s and R_p, were determined by fitting the charge transient responses to the current-time response of the equivalent circuit.

Fig. 1 Top: equivalent circuit for the supercapacitor system. C_{sp}: capacitance; R_p: parallel resistance; R_s: equivalent series resistance (ESR). Bottom: an example showing the fittings to the charge and discharge transients.

2.6 Mechanical characterisation of structural power composites

Mechanical performance was investigated by carrying out the in-plane shear response by tensile testing of a ±45° laminate according to the standard ASTM D3518 [11]. It is recognised that a range of methods should be used to fully characterise the mechanical performance, but it was considered that this test would provide an insight into a critical

matrix dominated property for these materials. The dimensions of the composite specimens were 150×25 mm. Glass-fibre composite end-tabs were applied on both ends of specimens, leading to a gauge length of 90 mm. In order to measure the strains in both the longitudinal and transverse directions, a biaxial strain gauge (FCA-5-11, Techni Measure) was adhered to the sample using cyanoacrylate glue at the mid-span of the specimens. The tests were conducted at room temperature using an INSTRON 4505 universal testing machine, equipped with a 1 kN load cell, with a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min. A minimum of five measurements were performed for each type of specimen. The fibre volume fraction was measured according to the standard ASTM D3171 Method II [12].

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Fabrication and characterization of CAG-modified carbon fabrics

A typical CAG-loading of around 9.5 wt.% was obtained. SEM characterisation demonstrated relatively uniform coating of CAGs on the carbon fibre fabrics (Fig. 2a, b). The gaps between carbon fibres within fibre bundles were also successfully filled with CAGs (Fig. 2c), which themselves possessed an interconnected 3D porous structure with interstitial pores of a few tens of nanometres, leading to a hierarchical reinforcement structure.

Significant increases in pore volume were observed for the CAG-modified carbon fabrics during the N₂ adsorption measurements (Fig. 3). The CAG-modified carbon fabrics exhibited a hysteresis loop between the adsorption and desorption isotherms due to the formation of mesoporosity [13], a type IV curve shape according to the IUPAC classification [14]. The specific surface area significantly increased from 0.21 to 80.7 m²/g after the CAG modification (Table 1). The CAG-normalised surface area was around 850 m²/g, which is comparable to the typical values of CAGs reported in literature [15], in the range of 400-900 m²/g.

The electrochemical properties of carbon fibres before and after CAG modification were studied in aqueous solution via CV measurements based on a three electrode cell setup (Fig. 4). Both specimens possessed a relatively symmetric and rectangular shape, which is associated with pure capacitive behaviour [16].

Fig. 2 SEM images of (a) as-received and (b)-(c) CAG-modified carbon fibres.

Table 1 Surface properties of carbon fibre fabrics before and after CAG-modification and specific capacitances derived from cyclic voltammetry at a scan rate of 5 mV/s in aqueous electrolyte (3M KCl) using a three-electrode cell.

	as-received	CAG-modified
CAG loading (wt.%)	n/a	9.5
BET surface area ($\text{m}^2/\text{g}_{\text{-C+CAG}}$)	0.209 ± 0.003	80.7 ± 0.7
Pore volume (cm^3/g)	2.9×10^{-4}	0.138
Specific capacitance ($\text{F}/\text{g}_{\text{-C+CAG}}$)	0.06 ± 0.01	5.9 ± 0.4
CAG-normalised surface area ($\text{m}^2/\text{g}_{\text{-CAG}}$)	n/a	847.3
CAG-normalised capacitance ($\text{F}/\text{g}_{\text{-CAG}}$)	n/a	61.5

Fig. 3 Adsorption and desorption isotherms of as-received and CAG-modified carbon fabrics.

The specific capacitance derived from the CV measurements (Table 1) showed significant improvements, from 0.06 to 5.9 F/g, by introducing CAGs onto carbon fabrics. The CAG-normalised specific capacitance was also similar to the values reported in literature [15]. In addition, wider potential windows (up to -1 to 1 V) and higher scan rates (up to 100 mV/s) were tested and consistent capacitive behaviour was observed for the CAG-modified carbon fabrics.

Fig. 4 Cyclic voltammograms of as-received and CAG-modified carbon fabrics at a scan rate of 5 mV/s in 3 M KCl, based on three-electrode cell testing.

3.2 Structural power composites

3.2.1 Electrochemical characterisation of structural power composites

‘Proof-of-concept’ multifunctional structural power composites have been fabricated using an IL-modified solid-state polymer electrolyte, as a multifunctional matrix to provide both ionic transport and physical support. As a comparison, the devices were also tested in pure IL.

The CAG-based devices exhibited a lower ESR than the as-received carbon fibre-based control devices, which may be associated with improved transverse electrical conductivity between the carbon fibres, and a reduction in the interfacial resistance between the electrolyte and the carbon surface (please note that the as-received carbon fibres are sized initially). Improvements in specific capacitance, and hence the energy and power densities, were observed (Table 2) for the structural power composites containing CAG-modified carbon fabrics. However, these

increases were lower than those obtained in aqueous electrolyte (refer to electrode measurements in Table 1) or pure IL (refer to supercapacitor device measurements in Table 2). The limitation can be mainly attributed to the reduced ionic conductivity of the polymeric electrolytes. Higher energy and power densities are anticipated as the working voltage of IL could reach 4-7 V [17].

Table 2 Electrochemical properties of structural power composites based on polymer electrolyte of 10 wt.% IL in PEGDGE with as-received and CAG-modified carbon fibres and supercapacitors based on pure IL with the same electrode configurations. The energy (E) and power densities (P) were calculated using the applied voltage of 0.1 V. The coefficients of variation were around 5%.

Electrical properties	Electrolyte	as-received	CAG-modified
ESR ($k\Omega cm^2$)	10 wt.% IL in PEGDGE	23.7	14.7
C (mF/g)		10.7	71.2
E ($\mu Wh/kg$)		14.8	98.9
P (mW/kg)		2.64	3.84
ESR ($k\Omega cm^2$)	Pure IL	43.4	0.19
C (mF/g)		5.55	746.6
E ($\mu Wh/kg$)		7.71	1040
P (mW/kg)		1.44	300

3.2.2 Mechanical characterisation of structural power composites

The mechanical characterisation of CAG-based structural power composites was focused on the assessment of in-plane shear properties, which are mainly dominated by the matrix- performance and hence most likely to be affected by the CAG modification. In addition, the format of the shear specimens allowed simultaneous measurements of

electrochemical properties, without the need of large quantities of material. A benefit of CAG-modification in terms of mechanical properties was demonstrated; the CAG structure around the carbon fibres reinforced the surrounding polymer matrix, leading to significant improvements in in-plane shear strength and modulus, up to 3.2-fold. (Table 3). By comparing to the system with pure PEGDGE-based epoxy, it can be deduced that filling the pore structure of CAGs with IL had no apparent effect on the mechanical performance.

The reinforcing effects of CAGs demonstrated in current research suggest a promising route to improve the matrix-dominated properties of traditional fibre-reinforced composites (for example, interlaminar and in-plane shear properties), which is considered as one of the major limitations in the practical application of the traditional composites [18].

Table 3 Mechanical properties of structural power composites based on a matrix of 10 wt.% IL in PEGDGE with as-received and CAG-modified carbon fibres and composites fabricated using PEGDGE-based epoxy with the same fibre reinforcements.

Mechanical properties	Matrix	as-received	CAG-modified
Shear strength (MPa)	10 wt.% IL in PEGDGE	5.36 ± 0.07	8.71 ± 0.11
Shear modulus (MPa)		276 ± 14	895 ± 60
Fibre volume fraction (vol.%)		47.2	42.0
Shear strength (MPa)	PEGDGE-based epoxy	5.83 ± 0.14	8.88 ± 0.12
Shear modulus (MPa)		201 ± 10	911 ± 60
Fibre volume fraction (vol.%)		47.2	42.0

4 Conclusions

A new hierarchical composite microstructure has been created by embedding structural carbon fabrics into a continuous network of CAGs to form a coherent but porous monolith. The CAG-modified carbon fabric structure could provide excellent structural mechanical properties whilst possessing a high electrochemical surface area suitable for electrochemical energy storage. 'Proof-of-concept' structural power composites based on CAG-modified structural carbon fabrics have successfully demonstrated improvements in the multifunctional characteristics of the system; the CAG-modification not only improved the electrochemical surface area and capacitance, but also reinforced the polymer matrix surrounding the fibres, leading to significant improvements in the matrix-dominated composite properties. In addition, CAG provides an additional reinforcing effect, suggesting an opportunity to enhance the mechanical characteristics of traditional fibre-reinforced structural composites.

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